

Holographic Design of Arbitrary Multi-Beam Leaky-Wave Antennas

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Abstract— This paper proposes a versatile method for designing arbitrary multi-beam leaky-wave antennas that can be applied to the synthesis of different beams with different gains, or of more than two beams. The method is based on superposing multiple objective field patterns in the context of the holographic design of a modulated impedance surface. In particular, dual-beam leaky-wave antennas with equal beam gains, and with relative gain differences of 3dB and 6dB are demonstrated through full-wave simulations. In addition, the method has been experimentally validated by the fabrication of the design with equal beam gains. A good agreement between measurements and simulations has been observed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The densification proposed for future 5G networks is increasing the complexity of wireless fronthaul and backhaul networks. On the antenna side, low cost solutions capable of providing energy efficient point-to-multipoint (P2MP) communications are of interest for aggregation sites. Traditionally, P2MP is achieved using sectorial antennas on the concentrator node, but a multi-beam antenna solution would allow reducing the transmit power and the interference levels. In this context, leaky-wave antennas (LWAs) may constitute a low cost alternative to traditional arrays, since they do not require complex beamforming networks. Here it is assumed that the limited bandwidth provided by LWAs covers the lower requirements of the communication systems.

Linear dual-beam LWAs were proposed either by feeding the antenna through a single port located at its midpoint [1] or through two ports located at both antenna ends [2]. However, both solutions provide two symmetric beams with respect to the antenna boresight, which might not meet the needs a a general P2MP configuration. This limitation was circumvented by the authors in [3] that proposed a method for the arbitrary design of dual-beam LWAs based on the excitation of two leaky-wave modes. The complexity of this method may increase when attempting to synthesize more than two beams or beams with unequal gains, due to the need of controlling the propagation characteristics of several leaky-wave modes at the same time.

In this paper, we propose a versatile method for designing multi-beam LWAs, not restricted to dual-beam solutions and capable of controlling the relative gains of each synthesized beam. It is based on applying superposition to the holographic design of artificial impedance surfaces [4]. Since we address one-dimensional LWAs, the method can be also interpreted as the design of a surface reactance modulated by the superposition of multiple sinusoidal waveforms [5]. A similar method has been recently presented in [6] for 2-D metasurface antennas, but it has not been applied to LWAs nor experimentally demonstrated. Moreover, it does not discuss the synthesis of unequal beam gains nor strictly follows the holographic principle as claimed in [7].

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the multi-beam design method, Section 3 addresses the specific design and simulation of multi-beam antennas with equal and unequal beam gains and Section 4 presents the experimental validation. Finally, Section 5 concludes the work.

2. MULTI-BEAM DESIGN METHOD

The holographic design principle of artificial surface impedance antennas consists of creating the subwavelength pattern of the surface impedance as the interference pattern between the field required in the antenna surface to create the desired radiation pattern (ϕ_{obj}), and the illuminating surface wave (ϕ_{sw}) [4]. In this way, when this surface is excited with the expected surface wave, the hologram is created and the desired radiation pattern is synthesized. For a LWA placed along the x-axis and fed at $x = 0$, the surface wave can be expressed as

$$\Phi_{sw} = e^{-jknx}, \quad (1)$$

where k is the wavenumber and $n = \sqrt{1 + X^2}$ is the refractive index of the surface wave, with X being the normalized average surface reactance. In order to synthesize a single beam towards θ_0 the required field at the antenna surface can be expressed as the steering vector

$$\Phi_{obj} = e^{-jkx \sin \theta_0}. \quad (2)$$

Therefore, multiple beams can be synthesized by patterning the surface impedance as the interference pattern of the exciting surface wave and the superposition of the steering vectors to every desired angle ($\phi_{obj,i}$); hence

$$Z(x) = j\eta \left[X + M\mathcal{R} \left(\left(\sum_i^N a_i \phi_{obj,i} \right) \phi_{sw}^* \right) \right]; \quad (3)$$

where η is the free-space impedance; M is the so-called index of modulation; \mathcal{R} stands for the real part and a_i is the amplitude coefficient of beam i .

Equation (3) can be easily developed to show that the surface reactance must be modulated by the superposition of multiple sinusoidal waveforms. Similarly, the multi-beam design principle can be interpreted as the superposition of multiple -1 leaky-wave harmonics. This interpretation makes evident that the impact of the chosen X and M values will be the one described in [5]. In particular, a high value for X is desired in order to avoid the appearance of undesired higher order leaky-wave harmonics; whereas M controls the leakage rate of the propagating leaky-wave and thus the illumination of the antenna surface. It is important to remark here that, in order to preserve the function of M , the amplitude coefficients in (3) must obey $\sum a_i = 1$; otherwise we are effectively changing the value of M .

The amplitude coefficients can be arranged in order to synthesize different beams with different gains. In this case, the gain difference between beam i and j fulfills $\Delta G_{ij} = 20 \log \left(\frac{a_i}{a_j} \right)$. It is worth mentioning that the radiated energy is divided among the different synthesized beams, so a gain reduction of 3 dB must be expected every time we double the number of beams with equal gains. Therefore, the increase of the number of beams requires an efficient illumination of longer LWAs in order to keep radiation characteristics such as gains or sidelobe levels. Due to the limitations of our hardware, we can not simulate very long antennas with enough accuracy, thus the remainder of the paper will focus on dual-beam designs.

3. ANTENNA DESIGN AND SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to implement the surface reactance distribution derived by (3), a similar design procedure to [5] is followed. The evaluated antennas in this paper consist of 80 $\lambda/10$ unit cells based on two metal strips separated by a small gap; on top of a grounded dielectric slab. By changing the width of the gap, we are able to synthesize the desired surface reactance according to (3). In contrast with [5] that used a thick dielectric, the required high value of X is obtained here by using a material with high dielectric constant and a more usual dielectric thickness. In particular, an Arlon AD1000 substrate with $\epsilon_r = 10.2$ and 1.27mm of thickness is used. Figure 1(a) depicts the mapping between the size of the gap and the surface reactance, whereas Fig. 1(b) shows the simulated unit cell. The mapping curve was obtained through the method described in [5], which involved the simulation of a unit cell in periodic boundary conditions. These simulations were performed with ANSYS HFSS, at an operating frequency of 18 GHz and unit cell dimensions of 1.66mm x 1.66mm.

As shown in Fig. 2, the unit cells are placed along the x-axis, and the dimensions of the metal strips on the y-axis are enlarged to λ (16.6mm). The antenna is fed from one side by a microstrip line through an exponential taper to assure a good impedance adaptation. As a difference to [5], the other antenna end is not terminated with another port and a 50 Ω load, but it is left open. This solution simplifies the design and the simulation, though the surface wave reflection on the open-end must be controlled in order to minimize the appearance of reflected beams.

In order to verify the design method, we used ANSYS HFSS to simulate the whole structure of a dual-beam antenna pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$ with equal beam gains (i.e. $a_1 = a_2 = 0.5$); $X = 1.8$; and $M = M_{ref}$, which is expressed as

$$M_{ref}(n) = \begin{cases} 0.2 + 0.00513n & \text{if } n < 40 \\ 0.4 & \text{if } n \geq 40; \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: (a) Mapping between surface reactance and gap width; (b) Unit cell

Figure 2: Simulated dual-beam LWA pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$, with $X = 1.8$ and $M = M_{ref}$ following (4).

where n stands for the unit cell index that spans from 0 to 79. This index modulation distribution was found to provide the best gain results for a single-beam antenna. The main idea behind it is to reduce the leakage at the beginning, allowing the illumination of the whole antenna, while reducing the reflection at the end by keeping a large leakage rate on its second half.

Figure 3(a) depicts the simulated E-plane radiation pattern at 18 GHz. The two beams are synthesized at the desired angles with gains of 11.9dB at 28° and 10.9dB at -15° . The elimination of this 1dB difference would require a fine tuning of the a_i values. The sidelobe level is around -9dB, which in fact is a very good figure, considering that single beam LWA hardly present sidelobe levels below -10dB. Remarkably, the M_{ref} value which was optimized for the single-beam case, is not optimal here, since the surface reactance is modulated by an already modulated sine wave, as shown in Fig. 3(b). This issue is confirmed also in Fig. 3(a) which demonstrates that larger gains can be obtained by increasing the M values above M_{ref} .

The versatility of the method is further demonstrated by the design of two dual-beam antennas, also pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$ but with unequal beam gains. In particular, a gain difference of $\Delta G = 6$ dB is targeted by using $a_1 = 2/3$ and $a_2 = 1/3$; and $\Delta G = 3$ dB by $a_1 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{1+\sqrt{2}}$ and $a_2 = \frac{1}{1+\sqrt{2}}$. The values of X and M are set to 1.8 and M_{ref} , respectively. Figures 4(a) and 4(b) depict the simulated radiation patterns and the surface reactance distributions, respectively. The case of equal gain beams is also shown as a reference. It can be observed that the simulated gain beams almost match the targeted ones; hence, a gain difference of $\Delta G = 7.1$ dB is obtained for the 6dB case, whereas $\Delta G = 4$ dB is obtained for the 3dB case. In both cases, the 1dB difference between the target and the simulated figures matches the difference already observed for the equal gains case.

4. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The antenna design depicted in Fig. 2 has been fabricated and measured in a far-field anechoic chamber. Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show the E-plane measured radiation pattern and a picture of the fabricated LWA, respectively. The simulated radiation patterns are also included for comparison. A reasonable agreement is observed between simulation and measurements, which demonstrates the

Figure 3: Simulations results for a dual-beam antenna pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$, with $X = 1.8$, different M values and equal beam gains; (a) Radiation pattern ; (b) Surface reactance

Figure 4: Simulations results for a dual-beam antenna pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$, with $X = 1.8$, $M = M_{ref}$ and unequal beam gains; (a) Radiation pattern ; (b) Surface reactance

feasibility of the proposed method. The measured beams are synthesized at the expected angles but the measured gain difference is enlarged to 2dB, which reinforces the need of fine tuning the amplitude coefficient values in order to obtain perfectly equal beam gains. In addition, the dynamic range of the measurement set up at 18 GHz is affecting the sidelobes, what explains the noisy pattern and part of the discrepancies in these zones.

5. CONCLUSION

This work presented an arbitrary multi-beam design method for LWAs based on the holographic and superposition principles. The versatility of the method has been demonstrated by the design and simulation of dual-beam LWAs with equal gain beams, and with gain differences of 3dB and 6dB. Moreover, the design with equal gain beams has been fabricated and measured, and a good agreement between simulations and measurements has been achieved. Two additional conclusion can be extracted from this study. First, the need of optimizing the index of modulation for the multiple-beam case, since the performance of index of modulations optimized for the single-beam case are significantly affected. Second, the requirement of fine tuning the amplitude coefficients of each beam in order to achieve exactly the desired relative gains.

A potential field of application of these antennas are point-to-multipoint communications in future dense backhaul and fronthaul networks.

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Figure 5: Dual-beam antenna pointing towards $\theta_1 = 28^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = -15^\circ$, with $X = 1.8$, $M = M_{ref}$ and equal beam gains; (a) Measured E-plane radiation pattern ; (b) Antenna picture

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REFERENCES

1. C. Luxey and J. M. Latheurte. Simple design of dual-beam leaky-wave antennas in microstrips. *IEE Proceedings - Microwaves, Antennas and Propagation*, 144(6):397–402, Dec 1997.
2. Chien-Jen Wang, C. F. Jou, and Jin-Jei Wu. A novel two-beam scanning active leaky-wave antenna. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 47(8):1314–1317, Aug 1999.
3. Z. L. Ma and L. J. Jiang. One-dimensional triple periodic dual-beam microstrip leaky-wave antenna. *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, 14:390–393, 2015.
4. B. H. Fong, J. S. Colburn, J. J. Ottusch, J. L. Visher, and D. F. Sievenpiper. Scalar and tensor holographic artificial impedance surfaces. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 58(10):3212–3221, Oct 2010.
5. A. M. Patel and A. Grbic. A printed leaky-wave antenna based on a sinusoidally-modulated reactance surface. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 59(6):2087–2096, June 2011.
6. D. Gonzalez-Ovejero, G. Minatti, G. Chattopadhyay, and S. Maci. Multibeam by metasurface antennas. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 65(6):2923–2930, June 2017.
7. G. Minatti, M. Faenzi, E. Martini, F. Caminita, P. De Vita, D. Gonzalez-Ovejero, M. Sabbadini, and S. Maci. Modulated metasurface antennas for space: Synthesis, analysis and realizations. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 63(4):1288–1300, April 2015.